

EFFECT OF COMPOST MADE BASED ON TOBACCO INDUSTRY WASTE ON
PLANT PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract. Experiments aimed at studying the effect of compost made on the basis of tobacco waste on the productivity of plants are studied on the example of a wheat plant.

Key words: composting, tobacco, humus, garbage, dust.

If we compare the microelement composition of the soil composition and the microelement composition of the tobacco industry waste, which is the object of our research, the most common microelements in the soil composition (i.e. Zn and Mn) are twice as high in the tobacco industry waste. At the same time, a number of microelements that are found in large quantities in the tobacco industry waste (for example, Fe, Ca and K) are almost absent in the soils of the Khatirchi district studied by us [3].

Human life is inextricably linked with the natural environment surrounding it, and sources confirming this are found at every step. The scientific and technological revolution, which is rapidly taking place on a global scale, has a positive impact on improving people's working conditions and living standards, but the ecological changes it has caused, in turn, have a complex impact on humanity and on Mother Nature, which supports it [1].

According to accurate data, each person currently leaves 1m³ of garbage in their daily lives per year. If such a large amount of waste is seen in a city or republic, then one can imagine how polluted our environment is. Along with the above, industrial waste is a source of environmental pollution that causes various diseases in humans and leads to ecological degradation of mother nature [2].

Industrial waste and other household waste have been circulating in the environment for many years, moving from one environment to another. For example, lead and DDT do not disappear on their own over time, but accumulate in some part of nature. Some aggressive substances circulate throughout the planet. For example, there is information that 2,500 tons of DDT have accumulated in the Antarctic glaciers, where humans have never stepped foot. Dust, smoke, soot, and fog in the atmospheric air of large cities and

industrial centers with highly developed industries sometimes block sunlight and prevent ultraviolet rays from reaching the earth's surface [3].

Tobacco industry waste is one of the wastes that has a negative impact on human health and the environment. In order to neutralize and rationally use tobacco industry waste, it is effective to ferment it with soil bacteria, prepare compost, and use it to increase plant productivity.

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